

Buğday Sapı Hamurlarının Oksijen ile Ağartılmasında Ksilanaz Enziminin Etkileri

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Özet

Bu çalışmada çevre dostu yöntemlerle buğday saplarından elde edilen kağıt hamurlarının ağartılmasında ksilanaz enziminin etkileri araştırılmıştır. Kağıt hamuru üretiminde buğday sapları Soda-Hava-Potasyum borhidrür (KBH₄) yöntemiyle pişirilmiştir. Optimum enzim uygulamasını belirlemek için buğday sapı hamurlarına belirli koşullarda dört farklı oranda (0, 5, 10, 15 U/g) enzim uygulanmıştır. En iyi sonuçları veren enzim uygulaması sonrası enzimin etkilerini belirlemek için kağıt hamurları bir kademe ağartma işlemine tabi tutulmuştur. Enzim uygulanmış ve uygulanmamış kağıt hamurları 7 bar oksijen ile ağartılmıştır. Ağartma işlemi sonrası hamurların verimi, kapa numarası, viskozite değerleri ve optik özellikleri incelenmiştir. Çalışma sonucunda, enzim uygulanmış hamurların oksijen ile ağartılması sonrası enzim uygulanmamış hamurlara göre beyazlık ve parlaklık değerleri sırasıyla %10.1 ve %13.3 oranlarında artarken, sarılık değerleri ise %6.3 oranında azalmıştır. Sonuç olarak, buğday saplarından elde edilen kağıt hamurlarının ağartılmasında ksilanaz enzim uygulamasının bir sonraki ağartma kademesinde optik özellikler üzerine belirgin bir etkisi vardır. Ağartma işlemlerinde ksilanaz enzimi kullanılarak hem daha iyi sonuçlar alınabilir hem de bir sonraki ağartma kademesinde daha az kimyasal kullanılabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Ağartma, Buğday sapı, Kağıt hamuru, Ksilanaz.

Effects of Xylanase Enzyme on Oxygen Bleaching of Wheat Straw Pulp

Abstract

In this study, the effects of xylanase enzyme on the wheat straw pulp bleaching were investigated. Wheat straws were cooked by Soda-Air-Potassium borohydride (KBH₄) method in order to pulp production. The pulps were applied to xylanase enzyme in four different ratios (0, 5, 10, 15 U/g) to determine optimum condition. Then, the pulps obtained from optimum condition were subjected to a bleaching process to determine the effects of the enzyme. Enzyme treated and untreated pulps were bleached with 7 bar oxygen. Yield, kapa number, viscosity values and optical properties of the pulps were investigated after bleaching. The obtained results

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indicated that the brightness and whiteness values of the enzyme treated pulps increased about 10.1% and 13.3%, respectively and the yellowness values decreased about 6.3% compared to the untreated pulps after oxygen bleaching. Consequently, xylanase enzyme application in the bleaching of pulp obtained from wheat stalks has a significant effect on the optical properties in the next bleaching stage. In bleaching processes, xylanase enzyme can be used for better results and less chemical can be used at the next bleaching stage.

Keywords: Bleaching, Pulp, Wheat straw, Xylanase.

1. Introduction

Enzyme application is an environment-friendly biological bleaching method which is used to prevent or reduce the use of chlorinated bleaches. The most effective and common enzyme used in enzymatic bleaching is xylanase enzyme. Xylanase breaks down the covalent bonds between the hemicellulose and lignin found in the pulp and releases lignin and chromophores. It also provides for the re-polymerization of the re-precipitated xylylans onto the fibers after cooking and facilitates the penetration of bleaching chemicals in the subsequent bleaching stages (Bajpai et al., 1999). Although the mechanism of the xylanase enzyme cannot be fully explained, different hypotheses have emerged. The first hypothesis is that the xylylans which are deposited in the pulp after the cooking process make access to lignin difficult (Fig. 1). Xylanase enzymes facilitate the access to lignin by degrading the precipitated xylylans.

Figure 1. The effect of xylanase on xylylans

Xylanases are able of degrading xylose and xylylans in oligosaccharides. The lignin-carbohydrate complex (LCC) is damaged during the deterioration of xylylans and more active groups are consisted. Meantime, the fiber cell wall relaxes and assists in the exposure of lignin to bleaching agents and alkalis, thereby improving the bleachability of the pulps (Maan and Dutt, 2017). The main objectives of the use of enzymes in pulp bleaching are to accelerate the removal of lignin

at the next bleaching stage and to contribute to the protection of both the economy and the environment by using fewer chemicals in bleaching processes.

Wheat (*Triticum*) in the gramineae family is an annual herbaceous plant breeding. According to many studies, the gene center of the wheat has been accepted as Anatolia, Caucasus and West Iran. It is preferred as a place of cultivation and it is considered as the basic nutrient used in flour and feed production. In terms of world wheat production, China ranked first with 131.5 million tons of wheat production in 2016 and Turkey ranked 11th with 20.6 million tons. Wheat production in the world is approximately 7.5 billion tons and our country meets 2.74% of this amount (FAO, 2018). According to the researches and agriculturalists, approximately 2 kg of wheat stalk is obtained from 1 kg of wheat produced place (Akgul, 1997; Cicekler, 2012; Tutus and Cicekler, 2016). In 2017, 21.5 million tons of wheat was produced in our country. Considering that 2 kg of straw is obtained from 1 kg of wheat production, 43 million tons of wheat straws are obtained in our country after the harvest. When baling and transporting losses and stubbles remaining on the soil after the harvest are taken into account, there is a loss of about 32% and this ratio varies depending on the height of the stubble and the type of transport. Approximately 68% of the 43 million wheat straws, 29.2 million tons, can be used. The nodes located in the wheat stem constitutes approximately 4-5% of the total straws weight and is not desirable since it is not sufficiently separated to the fibers in pulp production and is a sieve residue.

Unbleached pulps prepared by different methods are quite dark and not suitable for the production of many types of paper. Generally, paper pulp obtained by alkaline methods such as kraft and soda are dark. The pulps obtained by these methods are generally used in the production of wrapping paper. The pulps obtained by mechanical and sulfite method are generally light in color and are used in the production of papers such as newsprint. The lightest colored pulps are produced by the sulfite method (Smook, 1992). The brightness of the pulp is an indicator of its whiteness and is widely used as an indicator in the evaluation of the results of bleaching processes. Brightness is calculated from the reflectance of paper layers made from pulp using a specific spectrum band light with an effective wavelength of 457 nm. The bleaching of the pulp is carried out to achieve the specified degree of brightness, and the most important of these is to increase the brightness value of the pulp so that it can be used in writing-printing and tissue papers. The bleaching process also removes the residual lignin from the unbleached pulps and prevents yellowing when exposed to sunlight. In addition, the resin and other extracts contained in the unbleached pulp are removed during the bleaching process and improve the absorbency characteristic of the tissue paper (Farr et al., 1992; Fredette, 1996).

The aim of this study with using environmentally friendly methods was to investigate effects of xylanase enzyme on the wheat straw pulp bleaching and on the pulp properties.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

As the research material, wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) stems, which are the commercial names of Ceyhan 99 and the most widely distributed plants in our country, have been used. Straws were obtained from the trial sites of Kahramanmaraş Provincial Directorate of Food, Agriculture and Livestock. Xylanase enzyme purified endo- β -(1 \rightarrow 4)-xylanase from *Thermomyces lanuginosus* produced by submerged fermentation of a genetically modified *Aspergillus oryzae* microorganism was supplied from Sigma-Aldrich Inc. The other chemicals used in this study were provided from Merck KGaA Inc.

2.2. Pulp Production

After the weeds and other grain stalks in the wheat straws were cleaned by hand, the straws were chopped with a cutting tool to be 6-8 cm long, 1.5-2 mm thick and 20-25 mm wide. Cooking operations were made in 15-liter capacity, electrically heated, 25 bar pressure resistant, 4 cycles per minute and in the laboratory type discontinuous rotary cylindrical digester which can be controlled with thermostatically. Filling and unloading of the raw material into the digester was done by hand and 500 grams of wheat straw was used in cooking. The cooking temperature is controlled with the thermometer on the digester after the cooking process has been adjusted from the control panel and it has been worked with accuracy of + 2 °C. In the following Table 1, cooking trial was carried out.

Table 1. Wheat straws pulping conditions

Pulping conditions	Value
NaOH charge (%)	14
Air pressure (bar)	9
KBH ₄ charge (%)	0.7
Cooking temperature (°C)	140
Time to max. temp. (min)	40
Time at max. temp. (min)	50
Liquor to raw material ratio (L/kg)	5/1

The pulps obtained at the end of each cooking were washed on a 200 mesh sieve with plenty of water until the black liquor was removed. After removal of the chemical substances by washing, the pulps were disintegrated with a laboratory type disintegrator at a certain concentration for 10 minutes and screen rejects were eliminated in vibrating screen which has 0.15 mm slits.

Kappa number and viscosity of the pulps were determined according to TAPPI T 236 om-13 and TAPPI T 230 om-08, respectively.

2.3. Enzyme Application and Oxygen Bleaching

Enzyme application was applied to the pulps obtained by Soda-Air-KBH₄ method in different conditions given in Table 2. To stop the activity of the xylanase enzyme after application, the pulps were incubated at 100 °C for 10 minutes and prepared for the oxygen bleaching process. In order to determine enzyme application on the wheat straw pulp properties, enzyme treated and untreated pulps were subjected to oxygen bleaching under the condition given in Table 3 below.

Table 2. The enzyme application conditions

Conditions	Value
Enzyme charge (U/g)	5
pH	7
Temperature (°C)	40
Time at maximum temp. (min)	60
Concentration (%)	10

Table 3. Oxygen bleaching condition

Conditions	Value
Oxygen pressure (bar)	7
NaOH charge (%)	3
MgSO ₄ charge (%)	0.5
Temperature (°C)	100
Time at maximum temp. (min)	60
Concentration (%)	10

The pulps were gradually beaten in the Hollander Beater up to 35 °SR. Ten handsheets with the grammage of 70±3 (g.m⁻²), were prepared using a Rapid Kothen sheet former according to ISO 5269-2:2004. The brightness, whiteness and yellowness values of the papers were measured according to ISO/DIS 2470, ISO 11475 and ASTM E313 standards, respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Effects of Enzyme Application on Pulp Properties

The yield and optical properties of the enzyme treated wheat straw pulp were presented in Table 4. When the optical properties obtained after the xylanase enzyme applied to the pulps were examined, it was determined that the pre-enzyme application generally did not have a significant effect on the optical properties of the pulps. However, in many studies, it has been

reported that pre-enzyme application in multistage bleaching is effective at the next bleaching stage and decreases chemical consumption in bleaching processes, decreases cost and is environmentally friendly (Bajpai, 1999; Battan et al., 2007; Nagar et al., 2013).

Table 4. The yield and optical properties of the pulps obtained by enzyme application

Enzyme (U/g)	Whiteness (%ISO)	Brightness (%ISO)	Yellowness (E313)	Kappa Number	Viscosity (cm ³ /gr)	Yield (%)
0	43.78b	30.06b	44.41b	41.9	896	94.61
5	44.41a	32.00a	43.52a	41.5	875	94.00
10	44.46a	32.04a	43.56a	40.9	873	92.12
15	44.45a	32.16a	44.16b	40.5	870	90.25

*Mean values with the same lower-case letters are not significantly different according to Duncan's mean separation test.

Therefore, to determine the effect of xylanase enzyme in the next bleaching stage, the statistical analysis of Table 4 indicated that the enzyme ratios with optimal properties are 5 U/g to wheat straw pulp and these pulps were subjected to oxygen bleaching.

Since hemicellulase enzymes were indicated to be effective in the next bleaching steps, xylanase enzyme treated and untreated pulps were subjected to 7 bar oxygen bleaching and the yield and optical properties of these pulps were given below in Table 5.

Table 5. Findings about the yield, chemical and optical properties of enzyme treated and untreated pulps after oxygen bleaching

Enzyme (U/g)	Whiteness (%ISO)	Brightness (%ISO)	Yellowness (E313)	Kappa Number	Viscosity (cm ³ /gr)	Yield (%)
0	50.66	35.03	42.96	31.1	816	94.00
5	55.79	39.63	40.25	29.9	801	94.61

The kappa number of the enzyme treated pulps was found to be lower than that of untreated pulps about 3.6%. Kappa number is a parameter that indicates the bleachability or lignin content of pulps. The lower kappa number means that the pulps lignin content is lower; therefore, it is easy to bleach. The viscosity of a pulp is an indication of the average degree of polymerization of the cellulose. Therefore, it indicates the degradation of cellulose resulting from bleaching (reduction in cellulose molecular weight). According to Table 5, the enzyme application has no significant effect on viscosity value.

The effect of hemicellulases in bleaching processes is depend on the modification of hemicelluloses in pulp and increases the elimination of lignin in chemical bleaching. It has been suggested that the action of xylanase is due to partial hydrolysis of remodeled xylans or to the separation of xylan from lignin-carbohydrate (LC) complexes (Yang and Eriksson, 1992;

Kantelinen et al., 1993). Removal of xylans in pulp are known to facilitate the penetration to residual lignin, thereby increasing the bleachability of the pulp during the subsequent bleaching stages (Hortling et al., 1994). In addition, it is reported that hemicellulase applied to pulp also removes chromophoric groups (Patel et al., 1993). The effects of xylanases on xylan and their results were shown in Fig. 2 below (Jeffries and Viikari, 1996).

Figure 2. Suggested mechanisms of xylanase-aided bleaching.

Table 5 indicated that the whiteness values of the enzyme treated pulps were found to be higher than that of untreated pulps about 10.1%. Although whiteness, perception depends on many factors, it is a commercially important feature of paper and board. High whiteness increases the contrast of printed areas and increases the number of reproducible colors (Coppel et al., 2010). The brightness of the enzyme treated pulps was found as 39.63 %ISO and this value increased about 13.1% compared to untreated pulps. Brightness is not whiteness; it is not a colorimetric measurement. It is primarily a measure of freedom from pulp yellowness cohered with the existence of impurities and lignin left by partial bleaching. It is impossible to make a very white paper with pulps of lower brightness. The brightness test was designed primarily as a test to measure the effectiveness of bleaching in removing yellowness from pulps (Scott et al., 1995). Besides, the yellowness of the pulps was affected positively with enzyme application (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Effects of xylanase enzyme application on the wheat straw pulp properties

The obtained results showed that the enzyme application provide has been very effective in the wheat straw pulp bleaching. The xylanase enzyme breaks down covalent bonds between hemicellulose and lignin found in pulp and releases lignin and chromophores. In addition, it provides a re-polymerization of xylans which are re-deposited on the fibers after cooking and facilitates the penetration of bleaching chemicals in the subsequent bleaching stages. However, it also leads to loss of yield by dissolving hemicelluloses in the pulp. When Table 4 examined, the pulp yield was decreased about 4% with 15 U/g xylanase enzyme applications.

4. Conclusions

A significant improvement in the optical properties of the wheat straw pulp has been achieved by treating the pulp with xylanase enzyme prior to bleaching with oxygen. The brightness and whiteness of the pulps were increased and yellowness values of the pulps were also decreased by applying xylanase enzyme. The viscosity of the pulps has not been significantly affected during enzyme application and kappa number decreased with xylanase enzyme. Enzyme application is an environmentally friendly biological bleaching method which is used to prevent or reduce the use of chlorinated bleaching agents. Evaluation of enzymes in the pulp and paper industry both reduces the cost and the amount of chemicals used and environmental pollution. Therefore, various enzymes can be used in bleaching processes.

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